

Euphorbia dregeana Bergmelkbos

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© T. Makola

Group: Eudicot

Size: 1 - 1.5 m

Distribution:

Central Richtersveld Mountain Shrubland

Importance:

The Euphorbiaceae family is facing increasing threats in southern Africa due to poaching for illegal trade, with over 30 species currently classified as threatened and another 30 species either lacking sufficient data or yet to be evaluated. This highlights the urgent need for targeted conservation efforts to prevent further decline and avert critical risk.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 158.88 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 19.77 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 5.92 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 87.8%, Duplicated: 11.8%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 5 885.74 kilobases

Contig number: 3 075

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